

STUDIES IN EMULSION. PART I. DISPERSING ABILITY AND EMULSIFYING CAPACITY OF EMULSIFIERS

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Capacity of the emulsifier to emulsify a quantity of oils in different dilutions has been studied and the capacity to emulsify oil per unit weight of emulsifier has been found to increase with dilution. Specific interface also increases with the increase of the concentration of emulsifier solution.

Concentrated stable emulsions are not formed by simply dispersing oil in water. A third substance, which is called emulsifier, is necessary. When oil is dispersed in water the area per unit volume of oil, that is to say, the specific surface of oil is highly increased. According to Cooper (*Trans. Inst. Chem. Eng.*, 1938, 16, 131) the efficiency of an emulsifying machine is equal to

$$\frac{\text{Specific surface per g. of emulsion} \times \text{interfacial tension}}{\text{work done by the machine}}$$

If the work done by the machine be the same then the specific surface per g. of emulsion \times interfacial tension will be constant. With the decrease of interfacial tension specific surface will increase, *i. e.*, finer will be the dispersion. Fine dispersion is one of the factors that helps stability of emulsion. One of the important features of an emulsifier is to help fine dispersion. This function of an emulsifier then can be assessed, relative to another, from the knowledge of specific surface of the emulsions produced under identical conditions.

If the economic side is considered, the amount of oil emulsified per unit weight of emulsifier is as important as the quality of dispersion produced with its help. One and the same emulsifier may be used in various dilutions. King and Mukherjee (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, 58, 253) have shown that with the concentration specific surface increases. But hitherto no information is available about the capacity of the emulsifier to emulsify a quantity of oils in different dilutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Emulsifying Apparatus.—Emulsification was effected by agitating with a stirrer worked electrically. The stirrer consists of three pairs of blades. Pitch of the blades is 90°. The blades are fixed to the stirrer rod suchwise that second pair is perpendicular to the first and third is parallel to first. The lengths and breadths of all the blades are the same. Length is approximately 1¼" and breadth ½". There is no gap between the two pairs of blades. The diameter of the vessels, in which emulsification was done, is 3½".

Process of Emulsification.—Some amount of water and emulsifier were placed in the vessel. The stirrer was allowed to work in the vessel practically keeping no clearance in the bottom. Oil was gradually added. When the oil was added extra 5

minutes' stirring was given. Then water was gradually added to dilute the jellies formed.

Determination of Interfacial Tension.—Relative values of interfacial tension were found with the help of Donnan's drop pipette. Oil was allowed to flow from a pipette placed at a constant depth in the liquid. The number of drops was counted for a definite volume of oil.

Size Frequency Analysis.—It was done by a Zeiss microscope. A slide of each emulsion was prepared from the diluted emulsion with 10% gelatin solution. Sizes of the particles were directly read under the microscope.

Properties of the oil used in making emulsions throughout the experiments are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Sp. gr.	0.9134 at 29.8°C.
Viscosity	111.6 Redwood secs. at 100°F.
Flash point	345°F. (Pensky Martin closed).
Macky test	96°C after 1 hour.
Chemical nature	Hydrocarbon oil from mineral origin.

TABLE II

Description of emulsifiers used.

- A. Oils of high fatty acid content and phenol.
- B. Rosin acids saponified with caustic soda.
- C. Rosin fatty anhydrides and sulphonated oil (conc.)
- D. Do (dil)
- E. Potassium soap of linoleic acid and linolenic acids with potassium rosinate in aqueous solution.
- F. Soap content as E, but with the addition of pale wool grease in a mineral oil base.
- G. Aqueous mixture of sodium linoleate and rosinate containing excess ammonia.
- H. Groundnut and castor oils plus neutralised protein treated by modified sulphonation and subsequent electrolytic action.

Na-oleate (2 g.) was weighed out in the vessel, requisite amount of water added to make it a particular soap gel of definite composition and 80 c.c. of the oil added dropwise in 20 minutes. The speed of the stirrer was kept between 800 and 850 r. p. m. Resulting jellies were so diluted that the emulsion produced had 20% of oil. Size frequency analysis of those emulsions was carried out and the results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Sizes.	Percentage of sodium oleate									
	5.	10.	15.	20.	25.	30.	35.	40.	45.	50.
0-1μ	5.8	6.0	2.2	5.3	9.8	19.4	25.6	28.5	47.8	52.0
1-2	17.2	21.9	11.4	19.1	30.0	45.8	50.0	49.5	39.9	36.5
2-3	31.5	27.5	32.2	35.3	43.3	29.9	20.8	18.4	9.9	9.9
3-4	15.6	15.8	27.8	31.3	14.1	4.4	3.1	3.2	2.1	1.5
4-5	10.8	10.1	16.6	8.1	2.2	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3
5-6	5.8	5.8	7.0	0.8	0.4					
6-7	3.9	4.1	2.0	0.1	0.2					
7-8	2.4	3.0	0.6							

TABLE III (contd.)

Sizes.	% Sodium oleate			Sizes.	% Sodium oleate			
	5.	10.	15.		5.	10.	15.	
8-9 μ	1.4	2.3	0.2	18-19 μ	0.2			
9-10	1.0	1.6		19-20	0.3			
10-11	0.6	0.9		20-21	0.1			
11-12	0.6	0.5		21-22	0.2			
12-13	0.5	0.3		22-23	0.1			
13-14	0.2	0.2		23-24	0.3			
14-15	0.3			24-25	0.3			
15-16	0.2			25-26	0.3			
16-17	0.2			Free oil	slight	slight	trace	
17-18	0.2							

TABLE IV

Specific interface.

Dilution of Na-oleate.	Sp. interface in sq. cm./g. oil.	Dilution of Na-oleate.	Sp. interface in sq. cm./g. oil.
5%	5.1417×10^3	30%	27.4495×10^3
10	10.0490×10^3	35	28.8767×10^3
15	18.0197×10^3	40	29.1881×10^3
20	18.3718×10^3	45	30.9744×10^3
25	22.2825×10^3	50	31.7346×10^3

Specific interface has been calculated according to King and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE V

Interfacial tension measurements.

Conc.	Drop numbers							
	A.	B.	C.	D.	E.	F.	G.	H.
0.1%	34	35	30	31	35	28	45	96
0.2	38	41	32	32	42	36	51	117
0.3	41	46	33	34	48	42	69	128
0.4	44	50	33	36	53	49	85	134
0.5	46	53	35	37	58	52	111	139
0.6	48	55	36	38	61	56	134	143
0.7	51	57	37	40	65	62	143	146
0.8	53	62	39	41	69	65		151
0.9	54	65	39	42	70	70		153
1.0	56	66	40	43	74	74	Streaming	155

Emulsion composition : oil, 300 c.c., water, 310 c.c. and emulsifier, 10 c.c.

TABLE VI
Size frequency analysis.

Diameter of the globules.	Size% of the globules in emulsions made with different emulsifiers :							
	A.	B.	C.	D.	E.	F.	G.	H.
0-1 μ	76.3	34.0	48.3	65.3	26.3	37.1	23.8	70.4
1-2	19.6	32.8	22.9	11.5	26.6	32.0	28.6	21.0
2-3	1.7	21.8	10.0	3.4	23.9	18.6	25.2	5.3
3-4 _c	1.5	8.2	9.7	5.3	16.6	8.2	19.8	2.0
4-5	0.2	2.1	1.4	5.2	4.1	2.1	1.6	0.5
5-6	0.1	0.4	1.8	3.3	1.2	1.4	0.3	0.2
6-7	—	0.2	0.7	1.5	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2
7-8	0.2	—	1.4	1.2	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2
8-9	—	0.1	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
9-10	0.1	0.3	0.6	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.1	—
10-11	0.3	0.1	3.0	1.7	0.1	0.1	0.1	—

TABLE VII
Specific interface.

Emulsifier used.	Sp. interface in sq. cm. per g. of oil.	Emulsifier used.	Sp. interface in sq. cm. per g. of oil.
A	13.9456×10^3	E	16.7918×10^3
B	18.0622×10^3	F	18.1042×10^3
C	9.1837×10^3	G	19.9483×10^3
D	9.5073×10^3	H	19.2652×10^3

Dilution of Na-oleate (% wt./V)	TABLE VIII										
	...	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50
Capacity in c. c. to form a jelly per g. of Na-oleate	...	1340	820	560	430	268	185	110	81	66	61

TABLE IX
Emulsoid jelly composition at the breaking point.

Oil (% by wt.)	Water (% by wt.)	Na-oleate (% by wt.)	Oil (% by wt.)	Water (% by wt.)	Na-oleate (% by wt.)
98.32	1.60	0.08	97.53	1.90	0.57
98.54	1.33	0.13	96.30	2.72	0.98
98.54	1.27	0.19	95.49	3.22	1.29
98.50	1.25	0.25	94.96	3.47	1.57
98.00	1.60	0.40	94.89	3.41	1.70

TABLE X

Dilution of Na-oleate (in %wt/V):	Total interface in sq. cm. at the breaking point.	Depth of molecular layer in No. of mols.
5	62.931760×10^5	1.53
10	75.266160×10^5	1.28
15	92.171520×10^5	1.05
20	10.547840×10^5	1.20
25	54.545544×10^5	1.77
30	45.383940×10^5	2.08
35	29.013600×10^5	3.32
40	21.594924×10^5	4.46
45	18.672720×10^5	5.16
50	17.682704×10^5	5.45

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Table III, it is found that with increasing concentration of emulsifier at the production stage of emulsoid jellies, where the actual dispersion is done, specific interface gradually increases. This goes to support King and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) who have shown that with the increase of concentration of emulsifier specific interface increases.

According to figures in Table V, emulsifiers may be arranged in gradation of their power of lowering interfacial tension as G, H, E, F, B, A, D, C. When they are arranged according to the specific interfaces given in Table VI, the series becomes G, H, F, B, E, A, D, C. The slight discrepancy which is noticed in the two aforesaid series may be overlooked due to the fact that the difference of drop numbers between E and F is practically negligible and that among B and either of E or F is not considerable. Considering jointly the drop number and specific surface of emulsions obtained by using industrial emulsifiers it becomes clear that capacity to lower interfacial tension is directly proportional to the specific interface.

Thus, the study of the interfacial tension will indicate the relative dispersive power of the different water-soluble emulsifiers.

Now the question is what will be the quantity of oil that can be emulsified per unit weight or volume of an emulsifier.

When oil is gradually added to an emulsifier solution and stirred, emulsoid jellies are produced. With the gradual addition of oil stiffness of the jelly increases with the consequence of increased tension in the adsorbed film. Addition of oil can be carried till the film breaks. The maximum amount of oil which a gram of sodium oleate can

emulsify at different dilution is given in Table VIII. Dilution of emulsifier solution favours emulsifying capacity. Obviously water plays a part.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

It has already been shown in Table IV that the specific surface decreases with dilution of emulsifier. So in case of concentrated emulsifiers total interface may be such that mono-molecularly dispersed sodium oleate film is not enough to cover it. But from Fig. 2 it is found that the total interface is highest at 15% and least at 50% emulsifier concentration. Also the figures in Table X, which have been calculated taking the dispersion at the breaking point of jellies equal to the dispersion at any other oil concentration and cross-section of Na-oleate molecule equal to 48×10^{-16} cm², point out that the molecular thickness of the film at the interface is highest when the capacity is the least.

The concentration of water, at the breaking point as given in Table IX and Fig. 1, is the highest when the capacity is the least. But it is a known fact that with slight dilution emulsions do not break.

Thus, the breaking of the emulsion is neither due to the increased specific surface nor due to the presence of increased percentage of water at the breaking point. It is likely that the property of the film changes with the concentration of Na-oleate. Either the want of sufficient quantity of water makes the film brittle or the number of molecules which orient in the interface decreases with the concentration.

CONCLUSION

With the increase of concentration of emulsifier solution specific interface increases. Relative lowering of interfacial tension may indicate relative dispersive power of soluble emulsifiers. Capacity to emulsify oil per unit weight of emulsifier increases with dilution.

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